

The Influence of Visual Merchandising and Hedonic Motivation on Impulse Buying Through Shopping Enjoyment as an Intervening Variable

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Abstract:

Consumer behavior in the market is highly dependent on ever-changing trends, making some people more hedonistic and motivated to constantly update their daily style by making unplanned purchases. It also influences the impulsive shopping habits of consumers. This study aimed to analyze the effect of visual merchandising and hedonic motivation on impulse buying mediated by shopping enjoyment. The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling, with a total sample of 226 respondents who used H&M products as one of the branded products in Indonesia. The analysis in this study was carried out using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method through AMOS 26. The main finding of this study was to show that visual merchandising, hedonic motivation, and shopping enjoyment had a positive and significant effect on consumer impulse buying when purchasing branded goods.

Keywords: visual merchandising; hedonic motivation; shopping enjoyment; impulse buying

1. Introduction

Globalization makes it easier for countries to trade abroad, including Indonesia and the rest of the world. Everything from abroad can enter Indonesia, including foreign fashion. The fashion industry in Indonesia is increasingly vibrant with the presence of new brands, such as H&M, the second largest retailer in the world, and multinational fashion brands. H&M sells products for everyone, including women, men, and children. This brand is available in 43 countries, including Indonesia.

Walters and White (1987) state, "... activities that coordinate the selection of effective merchandise through the effective display of goods". Therefore, product visuals are closely related to how products and/or brands visually affect consumers, and this also affects positive attitudes, namely shopping pleasure. It proves that buyers will only buy what they see. Visual merchandising is more than just window displays that attract customers. It can trigger consumers to enter the store and buy existing products. Since the 1950s, store vendors have strategically placed lower-priced items around the cash register (Bianchi, 2016). It is the same as what H&M does, which puts sock displays around the cashier. Of course, it is one strategy to attract the attention of consumers. Any product will be visible to shoppers as they pass through the store's front door (with the shelves pointing to the street) (Mowrey, 2017). In addition, Hedonistic motivation can also affect their impulse to buy due to the store environment (Hasmi, 2020). Currently, customers tend to have shopping behavior that not only influences them to make the right purchase but also helps them have a pleasant shopping experience. When people buy something, they experience two different emotions: hedonistic motivation and impulse buying. (Evangeline, 2021). It can be caused by the hedonic behavior inherent in each consumer. This trait gives rise to shopping enjoyment. It is an opportunity for companies to increase sales because the higher the hedonic nature appears, the higher the desire to shop for these consumers.

Stores must be able to create a good experience for consumers. The creation of a good experience in shopping can make someone do impulse buying. Dependence on always-changing trends makes some people more hedonistic and motivated to consistently update their daily style by making unplanned purchases (Pradhan, 2018). Highly impulsive consumers tend not to think about things, are easily attracted to something, and want satisfaction as quickly as possible (Aragoncillo & Orus, 2018).

Several previous studies have identified several factors that influence impulse buying, including visual merchandising (Karim et al., 2020; aw et al., 2010; Kerfoot et al., 2003; Crowley, 1993) and hedonic motivation (Dwikayana et al., 2021; Evangelin et al., 2021; Cinjarevic et al., 2011). Most research has studied store environments and impulse buying in developed countries, while research is still scarce in developing countries. An exploration like this allows us to understand the difference between developed and developing countries regarding impulse buying in the market. Based on these findings, the researcher wants to carry out research development on the effect of visual merchandising and hedonic motivation on impulsive purchases mediated by the enjoyment of shopping at H&M, a leading branded retailer in Indonesia.

2. Literature review

Visual merchandising is the placement of products carried out by the store by coordinating products and thinking about aesthetic aspects in building the store's image. Store appearance is the first thing that customers see, both interior and exterior, which gives a positive image of a business, causing attention, interest, desire, and consumer action. Visual Merchandising can increase store sales by adding visual excitement and an overall image that defines the store's business. (Kaur, 2013) found that 85% of consumers try on clothes found on displays. In visual merchandising, design characteristics become physical elements in the retail environment, influencing consumer emotions and purchasing decisions (Karim, 2020).

Hedonic motivation is a feeling that comes from an internal person to fulfill his desires. For example, someone will feel happy if they look at goods in a store; even if they do not buy, they will still do it to fulfill their desires. Hedonic motivation is based on the quality of the shopping experience rather than gathering information or purchasing products (Boedeker, 1995). Hedonic motivation can be defined as "behaviors that bring consumers to the market to satisfy their internal needs." (Jin and Kim, 2003, p. 399)

Shopping enjoyment is a characteristic of buyers who tend to think shopping is fun and allows them to experience greater shopping pleasure. Shopping enjoyment can result from a good shopping experience. Shopping enjoyment is also a factor for people who shop to make impulse buying. (Dwikayana et.al, 2021) state that shopping pleasure is defined as the pleasure obtained from the shopping process carried out by consumers.

Impulse buying refers to buying an unplanned response which then creates various emotions. Mowen and Minor (1998) define impulse buying as an unconscious reaction that increases the desire to acquire and possess and encourages consumers to make impulse purchases. According to Rook and Fisher (1995), impulsive buying refers to sudden feelings and strong and persistent desires that occur after certain stimuli that lead to intentional and unintentional purchases. A good shopping experience can lead to impulse purchases.

3. Theoretical basis

Several factors are why someone is compelled to make an impulse purchase, including internal and external factors. Internal factors exist within a person, namely mood and shopping habits, whether driven by hedonists or not. External factors that influence impulse buying come from the stimulus provided by the retailer, namely the store environment, store layout, and promotions offered by the store. Shopping enjoyment is a condition that encourages impulse buying. Shopping, which has become a pleasure for some people, is one of the drivers of hedonic motivation. Consumers who tend to be hedonistic will go shopping when they have free time or when they are having fun (Dwikayana *et al.*, 2021).

Analysis in this study was carried out using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method through AMOS 26. By using SEM, three types of analysis activities could be carried out simultaneously, namely checking the validity and reliability of instruments related to confirmatory factor analysis, testing the relationship model between variables related to the measurement model, and obtaining a suitable model for predictions related to structural model analysis. The overall fit of the model was measured by chi-square (χ^2), CMIN (The minimum sample discrepancy function) divided by the degree of freedom (df), root mean square residual (RMR), goodness of fit index (GFI), Tucker Lewis Index (TLI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Normal Fit Index (NFI).

4. Analysis

(1) Data source and collection

A total of 226 respondents were samples used in this study. The samples in this study were all consumers of H&M products. Respondents aged 15 years and over acted as connoisseurs in shopping and buying fashion products. H&M was chosen as the shop for the research. It is because it is included in branded products with prices that are quite affordable for everyone and are found in almost every city in Indonesia.

(2) Classification of variables and identification of parameters

The technique used in this study was Purposive Sampling, namely sampling based on specific considerations of consumers who had made purchases at H&M in the last six months. Determining data in this study was assisted by using a questionnaire. The questionnaire used a Likert scale on a five-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). The value variable of hedonic motivation was measured using 10 items (5 dimensions) stated by Arnold et al. (2003). Next, Visual Marketing is measured by 6 items proposed by Metha & Chugan (2012). Shopping enjoyment is measured using 8 items and 4 dimensions. Impulse buying consists of four items and 2 dimensions stated by Coley & Burgess (2003). Demographic information is collected for gender, age and occupation.

Table 1 Respondent's Characteristics

Kategori	Item	f	%
Gender	Male	85	38
	Female	141	62
	Total	226	100
Age	17 – 21 years old	86	38
	22 – 26 years old	85	38
	27 – 31 years old	55	24
	Total	226	100
Job	Student	34	15
	University students	81	36
	Civil Servants	52	23
	Entrepreneur	59	26
	Total	300	100

Table 1 shows that the respondents were all consumers who had shopped at H&M in the last 6 months. Women were more dominant in purchasing H & M products, aged 22 -26 years, and their job as university students.

(1) Measurement and Stuctural Model**Table 2 Measurement Model Result**

Items		Factor Loading	CR	AVE
Visual Merchandising	I feel compelled to enter a store when I see an attractive store display	0.84	0.96	0.83
	I tend to enter a store when an attractive front display attracts me	0.82		
	When I see the look of clothes with new designs on display, I tend to buy	0.85		
	I get an idea of what to buy after looking around in-store or at the	0.84		
	I tend to try on clothes that catch the eye when walking down the	0.80		
	Consumers are free to try H&M products on every aisle	0.84		
Hedonic Motivation	For me, shopping is an adventure	0.89	0.98	0.83
	Shopping makes me feel like I am in my own world	0.859		
	I like to shop with friends or family to socialize	0.874		
	I enjoy socializing with others when shopping for	0.908		
	When the mood is not good, I go shopping to make myself feel better	0.933		
	For me, shopping is a way to relieve stress	0.918		
	I go shopping to follow trends	0.918		
	I go shopping to see what new products are available.	0.945		
	Often, I go shopping when there are discounts/price cuts	0.906		
	I really enjoy bargain hunting when I shop for	0.914		

	I like to shop for other people because when they are happy, I will be happy too	0.908		
	I enjoy shopping for my family and friends	0.932		
Shopping Enjoyment	Strategic location	0.86	0.97	0.87
	Operational hours that make it easy for me to shop at H&M	0.87		
	The store atmosphere is pleasant	0.88		
	The pictures, as well as the colors in the store, make me happy shopping at the H&M	0.88		
	H&M is ready to serve with fast responses and solutions to every problem customers experience when shopping	0.87		
	H&M provides convenience to customers by completely categorizing each product according to its type	0.88		
	When I had trouble finding products, H&M employees were responsive	0.86		
	H&M provides a refund service for the convenience and safety of shopping customers	0.87		
Impulse Buying	There is a sudden desire to buy at H&M stores	0.82	0.94	0.84
	Difficulty resisting the urge to buy H&M products	0.87		
	Do not need to think long in deciding to purchase H&M products	0.86		
	There is not much to consider when purchasing an H&M	0.82		

Based on Table 2, the loading factor values for all items in the full model were above 0.50. It means that items consisting of hedonic motivation values and impulse buying were considered valid and were believed to measure the complete model construct. The reliability test also showed consistent results. All items in the value of hedonic motivation and impulse buying were also considered reliable and were believed to be able to measure the full construct model consistently. It can be seen from the average variance extract (AVE) value above 0.50 and the construct reliability (CR) value above 0.70.

Table 3 Index of Goodness of Fit

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut off Value	Results
χ^2 - Significance Probability	≥ 0.05	0.000
CMIN/DF	≤ 3.00	2.916
RMR	< 0.05	0.027
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.905
IFI	≥ 0.90	0.936
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.930
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.935

The model fit requirements can be accepted based on the goodness of fit (GOF) measurement results in table 3. The table also shows that there were six measurements that indicated a good degree of fit. CMIN/DF = 2.916 (≤ 3.00) and RMR = 0.027 (≤ 0.05) met the criteria. NFI=0.905, IFI=0.936, TLI=0.930, and CFI=0.935 were all above 0.90 and were sufficient to state that a model was fit and appropriate.

1. Construction of Model Structure Test

Figure 1: Full Model Structure Test

Table 4 Hypothesis Testing

Item	Std Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p-values	description
VM ---> SE	0.263	0.088	2.982	0.003	Significance
HM ---> SE	0.741	0.085	8.718	***	Significance
VM ---> IB	0.200	0.086	2.333	0.020	Significance
HM ---> IB	0.737	0.123	5.998	***	Significance
SE ---> IB	0.337	0.121	2.787	0.005	Significance

Based on Table 4, it can be seen that the t-score for the visual merchandising variable on shopping enjoyment was 2.982, which indicated a greater gain than the t-table of 1.96. Likewise, a p-value of less than 0.003 indicated a value of less than 0.05. It means that the first hypothesis regarding visual merchandising had a positive and significant effect on shopping enjoyment. The second hypothesis, the hedonic motivation variable t-score on shopping enjoyment, obtained a result of 8.718 and a p-value of less than 0.001. It proves that the hedonic motivation variable hypothesis had a positive and significant effect on the shopping enjoyment variable. The third hypothesis, obtaining the t-score value for the visual merchandising variable on impulse buying, obtained a value of 2.333 and a p-value of 0.020, indicating a value less than 0.05.

It means that visual merchandising had a positive and significant effect on impulse buying. In the fourth hypothesis, the t-value for the hedonic motivation variable for impulse buying was 5.998, and the p-value was less than 0.001. These results were consistent with the hypothesis that hedonic motivation had a positive and significant effect on impulse buying. The fifth hypothesis, the t-count value for the shopping enjoyment variable on employee performance was 2.787, and the p-value was 0.005, which indicated that shopping enjoyment had a positive and significant effect on impulse buying.

Furthermore, the indirect impact of the mediating variable is presented in Table 5, which contains the results of the Sobel test.

Table 5 Sobel Test – Significance of Mediation

Item	Sobel test statistic	Two-tailed probability	description
VM --> - SE ---> IB	2.037	0.041	Accepted
HM --> - SE ---> IB	2.653	0.007	Accepted

Based on the Sobel test results in Table 5, the Sobel test statistic value was 2,037, and a p-value of 0.041 on visual merchandising on shopping buying and shopping enjoyment on impulse buying. Hedonic motivation for shopping enjoyment and shopping enjoyment for impulse buying obtained a Sobel test statistic value of 2.653 and a p-value of 0.007. These results indicated that the statistical value of the Sobel test was greater than the t-table (1.96). Likewise, the p-value obtained was smaller than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). It shows that there was an indirect effect of visual merchandising and hedonic motivation on impulse buying through shopping enjoyment. Instead of being rational thinkers, consumers seek hedonic satisfaction as consumers feel happy and enjoy shopping in the shopping environment and prices offered by clothing stores (Karim et al., 2020). It demonstrates that hedonic motivation and visual merchandising could convert the nature of impulse buying to the impulsive purchase of branded product items.

5. Discussion

The higher the visual merchandising, the higher the consumer's shopping enjoyment. Store atmosphere and good product placement provide consumers with a good experience in shopping; of course, this creates shopping enjoyment for consumers. It is in line with research conducted by (Karim et al., 2020). Design characteristics are considered physical elements in the retail store environment that influence the consumer's emotional state and buying decision. Color is a significant factor in pleasurable feelings (Crowley, 1993).

The higher the hedonic motivation, the higher the shopping enjoyment. The hedonic motivation that comes from consumers makes them feel pleasure in shopping. Apart from the hedonic nature that comes from within them, shopping is an adventure for those who make themselves feel satisfied when shopping. This research supports previous research conducted by Horváth & Adıgüzel (2018), which discovered that hedonic motivation had a positive effect on shopping enjoyment. It indicates that one of the reasons for shopping enjoyment is to achieve satisfaction and pleasure. This, consumers who shop for pleasure are considered consumers who allocate more time to the shopping process and find the desired product. The higher the consumers shop with hedonic motives, the higher the level of information search for a product or service. It is because when consumers shop with hedonic motives, they will often seek information and feel pleasure in the search process.

High visual merchandising also influences high impulse buying. With a store atmosphere and good lighting, it would make consumers feel comfortable and make consumers spend more time in the store so that it is more likely for consumers to see all products, which can result in impulse buying for consumers. These results are in line with the results of the influence obtained by research conducted by (Lazim et al., 2020) which say that visual merchandising has a positive effect on impulse buying. The researcher claims that Visual Merchandising is all about displaying products in the most visually appealing way possible by focusing on communicating with customers through images and presentation. Visual merchandising is used to support brands, enhance products, increase sales, and be strategically located by adding visual excitement and imagery that defines and advertises a business store.

High hedonic motivation also results in high impulse buying as well. For people who have hedonic motivation, it is only natural that the impulse to shop. When consumers feel sad or stressed, they usually make impulse purchases. It makes them feel satisfied. This hypothesis has the same results as research conducted by (Dwikayana et al., 2021), meaning that an increase in hedonic shopping motivation results in an increase in impulsive purchases. Increasing hedonic shopping motivation means increasing consumer shopping motivation for travel, satisfaction, value, and social purposes, with the most dominant indicator in forming hedonic shopping motivation in the assessment of the shopping process.

This study found that high shopping enjoyment also had a high effect on impulse buying. When a person feels

comfortable, and a good store image is created, consumers will enjoy browsing products more in a good mood; consumers can carry out impulse buying activities. This study has results that align with the research conducted stated by (Dwikayana et al. 2021). The enjoyment of shopping has a positive and significant effect on impulse buying, meaning that the better consumers enjoy the atmosphere while they are shopping, the more they will build a positive attitude toward purchases.

6. Conclusions

(1) Summary

The results of the study show that visual merchandising and hedonic motivation have an effect on impulse buying. Building a good store image through the store atmosphere and appearance with hedonic motivation within consumers is the right step to make consumers impulse buy. Retailers, especially companies with branded brands, must continue to improve their ability to develop marketing strategies through store displays to enhance brand image and increase consumers' buying interest. In this case, the company must provide the correct information to its target customers.

(2) Policy suggestions

This information should be attractive to target consumers and contain information about the product's brand value, as well as create individual characteristics on the store display, so that target consumers are more familiar with the company's brand. It can be a consideration for company management to put more emphasis on store image through store appearance and take advantage of hedonic motivation in consumers in marketing products to users or the target market for branded products in Indonesia.

(3) Limitations

This study has limitations in the sample size used; only 226 respondents in this study may not be sufficient to represent the population, especially in Indonesia. Therefore, future studies are advised to rely on a larger sample. This study used three primary constructs. They were visual merchandising, hedonic motivation, and impulse buying. In addition, future researchers can examine different variables to develop more robust models of how impulse buying can be stimulated by consumers of branded products and marketers more generally. For researchers, the results of this study are expected to become literature and references to develop more in-depth and comprehensive research on impulse buying.

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